

Polarimetric properties of burned forest areas at C- and L-band

Mihai A. Tanase¹, Maurizio Santoro², Cristina Aponte³, and Juan de la Riva⁴

¹ Cooperative Research Centre for Spatial Information, The University of Melbourne

² Gamma Remote Sensing AG

³ Department of Forest and Ecosystem Science, University of Melbourne

⁴ Department of Geography, University of Zaragoza

Abstract

Fully polarimetric C- and L-band synthetic aperture radar (SAR) data have been investigated to determine the relationship between polarimetric target decomposition components and forest burn severity over two sites located in a Mediterranean environment. The dependence of the polarimetric decomposition metrics on SAR acquisition geometry and environmental conditions was also analyzed at C-band. Multiple linear regression models with interactions (i.e., the incidence angle was included as a predictor variable and its interaction with the radar metrics was accounted for as a multiplicative effect) were used to quantify burn severity retrieval accuracy. According to our experiment we found that for steep SAR acquisition geometries C-band polarimetric components related to surface scattering mechanisms had increased sensitivity to burn severity levels while for datasets acquired with more grazing geometries the polarimetric components related to volume scattering and dihedral scattering mechanisms were more correlated with burn severity levels. At L-band only volume and dihedral scattering related decomposition components provided significant relationships with burn severity levels. Relatively low burn severity estimation errors (less than 20% of burn severity range) were obtained for all datasets with L-band data presenting the highest sensitivity to fire effects. Using a single regression model provided sufficient accuracy for burn severity estimation when taking into account the local incidence angle. The use of fully polarimetric data improved the estimation accuracy of forest burn severity with respect to backscatter intensities by a small margin for our study sites. However, since backscatter intensity metrics already provide high retrieval accuracies whatever improvement was bound to be low.

1. Introduction

Changes in traditional land use patterns have modified the incidence of fires in many regions worldwide. Over half million hectares are annually burnt only in the European part of the Mediterranean basin, making fires an important environmental problem due to the greenhouse gasses release, forest and associated habitat loss and the economic loss caused by damages to existing infrastructure. The complexity of burning conditions causes large uncertainties for regional and global estimates of fire emissions. Remote sensing could provide the necessary boost to increase such estimates accuracy [1] using increasingly diverse sensors. Currently, there is a need to assess such orbiting sensors for their utility to quantifying fire effects on forests with burned biomass being directly related to burn severity levels which express fire effects on ecosystems. Nowadays burn severity levels can be estimated from both active and passive satellite sensors as shown by a variety of studies [2-5].

One of the most widely employed optical-based spectral index for burn severity assessment is the Normalized Burn Ratio (NBR) [6] used in a bi-temporal approach with pre- and post-fire datasets (dNBR). Differenced indices (e.g., dNBR) are sensitive to absolute and relative changes in forests structure, whereas single date indices (e.g., NBR) are more sensitive to post-fire forest structures such as vegetation fill, crown closure, and changes in average canopy height [7]. dNBR provides a scale of changes with respect to the pre-fire status, unburned area retaining values close to zero (i.e., little or no change). For some forest types optical based indices showed high potential for burn severity estimation at regional levels with the result not being site specific, and relatively easy to extrapolate over larger areas without drastically decreasing the estimation accuracy [8]. Nevertheless, reflectance based indexes often fail to produce accurate results especially for intermediate burn severity levels where multiple effects combine [8]. In addition, reflectance-based indices are also sensitive to plant phenology, solar elevation, and cloud cover which further decreases their utility in specific environments (i.e., at low and high latitudes) where monitoring severity trends over time and across regions is subject to higher estimation errors [9]. An alternative method for burn severity estimation is the use of synthetic aperture radar (SAR) images since they contain information directly related to the forest structure. Removal of leaves and branches by fire influences the radar microwaves with numerous studies confirming the relationships between synthetic aperture radar backscatter and fire effects in a range of environments from tropical to boreal [10-13]. Fewer studies dealt with burn severity retrieval most of them having as main objective fire-related ecosystem properties [14-16]. However, more recently, forest burn severity levels were studied in Mediterranean and boreal environments using backscatter [5, 17, 18] and

interferometric coherence [19] information acquired by multi-polarized SAR sensors. Such studies showed that fire affected areas could be reliably identified by SAR sensors and that burn severity retrieval is feasible under specific conditions related to sensor frequency and viewing geometry, polarization and environmental conditions [5, 20].

The availability of selectable SAR acquisition modes increased the interest in comparative studies which evaluate the benefits of fully polarized datasets over single- or dual-polarization acquisitions. Fully polarized datasets have the advantage of a complete description of the scattering process. Polarimetric target decompositions enhance or suppress contributions from specific scattering mechanisms allowing for improved retrieval of biophysical characteristics of interest. For vegetated terrain most decomposition algorithms assume a dominant scattering mechanism related to randomly oriented branches and trunk-ground interactions with an additional smaller, attenuated scattering component coming from the underlying surface [21-23]. For the particular case of a burned forest one expects decreasing volume and double-bounce components with increasing burn severity due to a reduction in scattering elements available at the crown level (leaves and/or branches depending on the radar wavelength). The amount of surface scattering would depend on the incidence angle with steeper acquisitions expected to present stronger contribution. Eigenvalue and eigenvector decompositions [24, 25] presume that each pixel is represented by a dominant scattering mechanism which can be used to extract information about the target. The dominant scattering mechanism is identified using a set of eigenvalues and angles. Usually, one uses eigenvalues to calculate ratios deriving further metrics such as H, A and α . The entropy (H) is a measure of the degree of randomness of the scattering process ($0 \leq H \leq 1$), with values close to zero indicating pure targets. The anisotropy (A) offers complementary discrimination information at high entropy values ($H > 0.7$) while the alpha angle (α) provides information on the main scattering mechanism ($\alpha \rightarrow 0^\circ$ single bounce, $\alpha \rightarrow 45^\circ$ volume scattering, $\alpha \rightarrow 90^\circ$ double bounce). For strong depolarizing systems such as coniferous forests high entropy levels and volume scattering are expected as C- and L-band waves interact more with small branches and needles and respectively larger branches. As burn severity increases entropy and alpha values should also decrease due to reduced scattering randomness and increased surface scattering.

The preference for a particular SAR frequency and acquisition mode (i.e., single or dual polarization vs. full polarization) will depend not only on the spatial resolution and swath extent (i.e., generally higher for modes acquiring fewer polarizations) but also on the accuracy of the retrieved bio-physical parameter. To date, no studies relating model-based polarimetric target decomposition components to forest burn severity are available. This work was built upon previous investigations on SAR backscatter and interferometric coherence response as a function of forest burn severity [5, 19]. The aim of this study was to increase the existing knowledge by providing an overview on polarimetric target decomposition components properties of burned areas for typical Mediterranean forests. The specific objectives were to i) investigate the signatures of common polarimetric target decomposition models (i.e., Pauli, Freeman-Durden, van Zyl, Yamaguchi, Cloude and Cloude-Pottier) as a function of burn severity, ii) evaluate the predictive power of polarimetric components for burn severity estimation and iii) assess the benefits of using fully polarimetric data over single or dual channel backscatter acquisitions.

2. Study area and datasets

The two forest fires (i.e., Zuera and Jaulin) for which fully polarimetric data were available are located in the central Ebro Valley, Spain (Fig. 1) which is characterized by a Mediterranean climate with continental characteristics. Most of the study areas stretch on moderate topography with the dominant land cover including forests interspersed with winter cereal crops. The vegetation is xerophilous, drought resistant and highly flammable providing abundant fuels after long droughts. Each of the two fires affected around 2000 hectares of pine dominated forests during August 2008 and July 2009 respectively. A general description of the vegetation types in the Central Ebro Valley and the areas affected by fires in recent years is given in [8] while more information on the forest structure and the two studied fires can be found in [5, 19].

The SAR dataset available for this study were acquired by the C-band Radarsat-2 and the Advanced Land Observing Satellite (ALOS) Phased Array type L-band SAR (PALSAR) sensors. Four fully polarized images were acquired by the Radarsat-2 sensor over the Jaulin fire at 28 degrees (2009.12.26 and 2010.01.19) and 43 degrees (2010.03.11 and 2010.04.04) incidence angle. For the Zuera fire one fully polarimetric PALSAR image was available (2009.04.28). In Table 1 the main characteristics of the SAR datasets together with the processing parameters are provided. All datasets were delivered as single-look complex images.

Composite Burn Index (CBI) plots were established in high-, moderate-, and low severity areas inside Zuera (123 plots) and Jaulin (45 plots) fire perimeters. Burn severity was evaluated, as described in [29], using the magnitude of the environmental change at each site with respect to the presumed pre-fire state. The CBI was designed to evaluate the magnitude of fire effects across all strata from an ecological perspective by evaluating the ground fire effects. The average conditions of vegetation are visually examined within a radius of 15 m, and the degree of change of each forest strata (i.e., litter, understorey and overstorey) with respect to the pre-fire assumed status is recorded in values from zero (no change) to three (100% change). Detailed information on the CBI plot assessment, together with photos illustrating the main burn severity levels in the study area is given in [8].

To aid the interpretation, meteorological data collected from Tauste (24 km south of Zuera fire) and Belchite (18 km south-east of Jaulin fire) meteorological stations (*Oficina del Regante* - Irrigation Office, regional government of Aragón) were used. The air temperature (at 1.5 m above ground) together with the relative air humidity ($H_{\%}$) at SAR acquisition time is presented in Table 2 for each meteorological station. Since the burned sites were located at different altitudes compared with the meteorological stations, the temperatures were adjusted with the environmental lapse rate (i.e., $-2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/300\text{ m}$). In addition, the reference evapotranspiration (ET_0) computed using the Penman-Monteith method [30] is also given. ET_0 expresses the evaporating power of the atmosphere at a specific location and is a climatic parameter computed from weather data. Accumulated precipitations (AcPp) were computed taking into account the last four days before acquisition. For the Zuera fire precipitation data collected by an automatic rain gauge installed roughly at the center of the fire perimeter were also available.

3. Methods

Two different types of metrics were derived from the SAR observations: the first group corresponds to backscatter intensity (i.e., BI metrics) and includes the intensity of individual channels (i.e., HH, HV, VH and VV) while the second group corresponds to individual components after polarimetric target decomposition (i.e., TD metrics). Pauli coherent polarimetric decomposition was used to separate the scattering matrix into simpler scattering responses related to single bouncing (HH+VV), double bouncing (HH-VV) and volume (2HV) scattering. Since the scattering matrix is only able to characterize pure scatterers, it is less useful for the characterization of distributed scatterers (i.e., forests). Due to the presence of speckle noise such areas are better characterized using second order (e.g., covariance and coherency matrices) polarimetric representations [26]. Through incoherent decompositions (i.e., Freeman-Durden, Cloude, van Zyl, and Yamaguchi) components with specific properties related to different scattering mechanisms were separated. Freeman-Durden [21], Yamaguchi [22], and van Zyl [31] decompositions model the coherency matrix as a function of three scattering mechanisms, surface scattering (Odd), double-bounce or dihedral scattering (Double) and volume scattering (Volume). In addition, Cloude-Pottier [25] eigenvector and eigenvalue decomposition was used to calculate the entropy (H), anisotropy (A) and mean alpha angle (α) from the coherency matrix while Cloude decomposition [24] was used to calculate eigenvectors related to the same scattering mechanisms as postulated for the surface scattering and double reflections by the Freeman-Durden decomposition [23]. One should notice that Freeman-Durden and, to a lesser extent, Yamaguchi decompositions may result in nonphysical results after the subtraction of the volume component. The volume component may be overestimated due to the assumption that neither ground return nor double bounce adds to the cross-polarized return. This assumption does not hold for slopes along-track directions which tend to rotate the polarization basis. The issue was recently dealt with (van Zyl decomposition model) by ensuring that all covariance matrices are positive by constraining the eigenvalues [23]. For detailed information about each modeling approach the reader is referred to the respective paper.

To reduce noise the polarimetric decompositions were carried out over a multi-looked (Table 1) coherency matrix which was subsequently filtered using a 3x3 window [32]. The multi-looked BI metrics and the TD metrics were geocoded to the UTM coordinate system (25 m pixel size) using a lookup table that described the transformation between the radar and the map geometries [27]. The lookup table was generated using a digital elevation model (DEM) and the provided orbital information of the SAR images. To correct for possible inaccuracies in the DEM and the SAR metadata, a refinement of the lookup table was applied, by correcting for possible offsets between the SAR images and a DEM based radar simulated image, assumed to correspond to the true map geometry. Prior to geocoding, the BI metrics were topographically normalized by correcting for the pixel area estimated from the DEM [28].

Due to the skewed distribution of the CBI plots towards moderate and high severity values and their relatively small area, the study was focused on a set surrogate plots (i.e., pseudo-plots) based on optical estimates of burn severity from Landsat TM data. The Normalized Burn Ratio (NBR) index combines reflectance of near and short-wave infrared (1), whereas the differenced Normalized Burn Ratio (dNBR) uses the difference between pre- and post-fire data sets (2) to isolate burned areas and to provide a quantitative measure of change with respect to the pre-fire status, with unburned areas retaining values close to zero. The consistency between CBI plots and remotely sensed dNBR estimates of burn severity was previously assessed at both sites [8] with high determination coefficients being found ($R^2 > 0.8$, $p < 0.001$) which supported the use of dNBR as a radiometric index highly related to the severity levels recorded in the field. A more detailed description of the Landsat TM image processing and acquisition dates for the Zuera and Jaulin study sites is given in [8].

$$\text{NBR} = (R4 - R7)/(R4 + R7) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{dNBR} = \text{NBR}_{\text{prefire}} - \text{NBR}_{\text{postfire}} \quad (2)$$

where: R is the per-pixel reflectance for Landsat Thematic Mapper (TM) bands.

The pseudo-plots were generated by averaging the intensity of nine SAR pixels with similar dNBR values and local incidence angles (rounded to unity) for each BI and TD metric. Similar dNBR values were obtained by reclassifying the continuous dNBR interval (-150 to 1050) into 24 dNBR classes. Past studies [17] showed that averaging nine pixels for each pseudo-plot appears to be optimal for the selected spatial resolution (25m) of the geocoded SAR images. In addition, maintaining the same number of pixels per pseudo-plot facilitates the results comparison with the previous studies [5, 19]. Depending on the SAR image, between 350 and 550 pseudo-plots were generated.

To understand the relationships between forest burn severity and TD metrics the dNBR based pseudo-plots were plotted as a function of burn severity in a 2-D space formed by metrics from each decomposition method. Correlation analysis was carried out to assess each TD metric against burn severity levels while the accuracy of burn severity predictions was assessed using multiple linear regression models. Such models were used to account for the effect of topography and at the same time avoid developing specific models for each local incidence angle. The local incidence angle (i.e., θ) was included as a predictor variable and its interaction with the TD metric intensity was accounted for as a multiplicative effect ($\text{TD} * \theta$). Thus, only one empirical model per TD metric and image was evaluated (3) as opposed to more than ten models used in the previous studies [5, 19]. The determination coefficient (model R^2), the root mean squared error (RMSE) and the determination coefficient between predicted and observed dNBR (predicted R^2) were used to assess which TD metric is better suited for burn severity evaluation.

For each model, the pseudo-plots were split in training and validation datasets using a 50/50 ratio. To keep a balanced frequency distribution only half of the unburned pseudo-plots were kept. This decreased the number of training/validation dataset to 300-450 pseudo-plots depending on the study site and SAR sensor incidence angle. The results were cross-compared to the BI metrics to understand the potential benefits of using fully polarimetric data for burn severity analysis. Since Radarsat-2 data were acquired at two different incidence angles it was also possible to assess the influence of the acquisition geometry on the scattering mechanisms and the estimation accuracy of burn severity.

$$\text{dNBR} = a + b * \text{TD} + c * \theta + d * (\text{TD} * \theta) \quad (3)$$

where: a,b,c - model coefficients, θ - local incidence angle, and TD - target decomposition metric

4. Results and Discussions

For each SAR sensor, 2-D feature-space partitions of burn severity levels are presented in Figure 2 for flat or nearly-flat areas (i.e., $\pm 5^\circ$ maximum slope). Metrics from each polarimetric decomposition technique as well as backscatter intensities were used to evaluate the sensitivity of C- and L-band data to burn severity. Since the Radarsat-2 datasets were acquired at different incidence angles two panels were included. Figure 2 shows that for steep acquisitions (i.e., 26° - top panels in Figure 2) it is difficult to separate burn severity levels using C-band regardless of the polarimetric target decomposition used: all burn severity levels largely overlap. Burned areas showed stronger returns (both BI and TD metrics) when compared to unburned areas largely due to the influence of SAR geometry acquisition and to some extent due to increased soil moisture after rainfall. At shallower angles (i.e., 43° - centre panels in Figure 2) the SAR metrics related to volume scattering (i.e., intensities of HV backscatter and volume scattering components) were considerably higher

for unburned and low burn severity forest which improved the differentiation of the fire affected forest areas. Most of the unburned forests were characterized by medium entropy levels with a dominant dipole scattering (i.e., volume scattering) while in the highly burned areas surface scattering dominated. One should notice that Radarsat-2 data were acquired over a forest characterized mostly by high and very high severity levels which did not allow for a balanced number of pseudo-plots by burn severity levels especially for low severity burn classes. We assumed that such areas would have been mostly characterized by intermediate values of volume scattering.

For our datasets, better differentiation was obtained using L-band data (Figure 2 bottom panels) for which there is a clear distinction between different severity levels in the 2-D feature space. The unburned and low severity areas were mostly characterized by volume scattering (i.e., medium to high entropy and dipole scattering) while the highest burn severities were characterized by lower entropy and alpha angle which imply a surface dominated scattering mechanism. There is a certain overlap between unburned, low and medium burn severities which represent the transitional nature of the fire effects in such areas: lightly burned tree crowns, scorching of intermediate-sized trees, partially consumed litter and the understory layer affected in a patchy pattern.

Figure 3 demonstrates the dependency of the decomposition target components (i.e, entropy and alpha angle) on the local incidence angle and to some extent on the environmental conditions for our study areas. The largest variation with incidence angle was observed for L-band data (bottom panels) which is explained by the higher wave penetration into the canopy and thus interaction with the underlying soil surface. For unburned forests (Figure 3 bottom left panels), at low incidence angles (i.e., steep viewing geometry) the scattering is characterized by small entropy and alpha angles indicating low scattering order (i.e., weak volume backscatter) and surface dominated reflections. From about 25 degrees incidence angle, diffuse volume scattering is dominant ($\alpha \approx 45^\circ$) and the signal is almost completely depolarized ($H > 0.9$) indicating multiple scattering from a cloud of loss symmetric particles (i.e., scattering from forest canopy). With increasing burn severity (Figure 3 bottom center panels) the backscattering behavior changes with scattering from the forest canopy dominating only at much higher local incidence angles (i.e., 55 degrees). For the remaining incidence angle intervals the backscatter is dominated by interactions between surface scattering and increasing canopy scattering. At highest severity and low incidence angle (Figure 3 bottom right panels) the backscatter is dominated by surface scattering mechanisms with weak volume scattering present after 25° due to canopy propagation effects. The lower penetration through the forest canopy at C-band (Figure 3, top panels) decreases the interaction with the soil surface with the backscatter being dominated by volume scattering over the entire range of incidence angles for unburned forests. With increasing burn severity H and α values decrease with backscatter being dominated by scattering mechanisms associated to canopy propagation effects. The C-band SAR datasets acquired under wetter conditions provided similar trends with the only difference being the slightly boost of volume scattering mechanisms at all incidence angles.

One should notice that the increased standard deviation observed for forests affected by medium burn severity is related to the high variability of forest conditions: i) for moderate-low severity levels the needles or leaves and the small branches of the short shrubs (<1 m height) are consumed by fire, whereas the tall shrubs (>1 m height) present scorched foliage. The tree crowns are partially scorched, which results in incomplete foliage loss, ii) for moderate-high severity areas, the consumption of the understory layer increases, whereas the tree crowns are usually scorched, with the foliage being retained only partially. The loss of branches and small twigs is small for the tree layer. The understory layer, especially the small shrubs (i.e., less than 1 m tall), loses twigs and small branches. In contrast, in high severity areas, the combustion of the litter, understory layer, and tree crown elements (i.e., needles and twigs) is complete while at the highest severities, small- and medium-sized branches are also consumed providing more homogeneous forest conditions.

The strength of linear dependency between burn severity levels and TD and BI metrics was computed using Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) presented in Table 3 (not significant relationships marked as *ns*). For C-band data acquired at low incidence angles (i.e., 2009.12.26 and 2010.01.19) there was a slight positive correlation (with increasing burn severity the SAR metrics increased) for all metrics but the H and α decomposition components. Among TD metrics, the highest correlations were recorded for those metrics related to surface (odd) or dihedral (double) scattering mechanisms. One should also notice the considerably higher r values recorded for the dataset acquired in a period with intense precipitations (2009.12.26) which suggest that at low incidence angles the effect of rainfall could enhance burn severity estimation confirming previous results obtained from ERS and ASAR backscatter intensity [5]. In addition, the HV backscatter

intensity showed relatively high correlations with burn severity after significant rainfall events while for the datasets acquired during a period with fewer precipitations (i.e., 2010.01.19) the relationship was not significant. Overall, better relationships with burn severity levels were observed for TD metrics ($r \approx 0.7$) with BI metrics presenting lower values ($0.4 < r < 0.6$).

For C-band data acquired at shallower incidence angles (i.e., 2010.03.11 and 2010.04.04) the intensity of the SAR backscatter metrics was negatively related to burn severity with the highest correlation values being obtained for the SAR metrics related to volume or dihedral scattering mechanisms. Although the two datasets were acquired under different environmental conditions (i.e., dry vs. wet) the impact of increased moisture on the correlation coefficients was low with the image acquired in dry conditions (i.e., 2010.03.11) showing only slightly better relationships with burn severity levels. Since for previous studies only C-band backscatter intensities acquired at low incidence angles were available it is difficult to assert the possible cause of this incongruence. On one hand it could be the result of smaller difference in the accumulate precipitations with respect to the dry acquisition and higher temperatures which increased evapotranspiration processes (Table 1). On the other hand, it could be reasonable to assume that the longest distance travelled by the waves through the forest canopy at higher incidence angles enhances the sensitivity of C-band data to burn severity compensating for the lack of sensitivity boost due to increase moisture content. BI metrics showed enhanced sensitivity to burn severity levels over TD metrics but the differences were relatively small. At L-band, the SAR metrics related to volume scattering mechanisms provided the highest correlation coefficients with burn severity. When comparing the two SAR frequencies one should notice the significantly higher r values obtained for L-band data (except for Cloude-Pottier decomposition). L-band SAR metrics related to surface scattering showed low or not significant relationships with burn severity.

To infer the utility of polarimetric decomposition components for burn severity estimation, multiple linear regression determination coefficients (model R^2) expressing the proportion of predicted burn severity variance (for the training dataset) and the RMSE (for the validation dataset) are presented in Table 4. In addition, the agreement between observed and predicted dNBR values was also included (predicted R^2). Higher model R^2 and lower errors were observed for the TD metrics related to surface scattering mechanisms for Radarsat-2 data acquired at low incidence angles. For the remaining datasets (i.e., C-band acquired at 43° incidence angle and L-band), the highest estimation accuracy was recorded for the TD metrics related to volume scattering mechanisms. As shown by the C-band data analysis, SAR acquisition geometry significantly influences the estimation accuracy of burn severity levels. Since the only image available at L-band was acquired at low incidence angle it is reasonable to assume that higher incidence angles at acquisition could enhance the differentiation of forest burn severity levels. In general, high model R^2 and low RMSE were obtained when estimating burn severity from TD metrics. However, for our datasets, the improvement of the burn severity estimation was only marginally better, with the model R^2 increasing by an average 0.07 and the RMSE decreasing by 2% when compared to BI metrics. Furthermore, for the Radarsat-2 data acquired at low incidence angles the estimation errors were sometimes higher and determination coefficients lower for TD metrics when compared to BI metrics.

The results presented here confirm previous studies [5] which showed that burn severity levels could be better estimated through SAR metrics sensitive to the volume scattering component. It also confirms that higher wavelengths are better suited for burn severity estimation and that steep SAR acquisition angles are less appropriate for monitoring fire affected areas especially for high frequency sensors such as C-band. This study demonstrated that a multiple regression model accounting for the interaction of the local topography can be used to estimate burn severity levels without losing significant precision over local incidence angle specific models. When comparing the results obtained for L-band data (i.e., HV intensity) with previous results [5] only slightly lower values are noticed for the R^2 and RMSE metrics: the R^2 decreases by 0.14 and the RMSE by 1-2% with respect to the average obtained for incidence angle specific models. This suggests that reasonable results could be attained by a common model if interaction effects of the incidence angle are taken into account. Compared with interferometric coherence [19], however, fully polarimetric data presented slightly less potential for burn severity estimation: model R^2 decreased on average by 0.2 and RMSE increased by 7% for L-band data. Such drops in the estimation accuracy could be partially attributed to the steeper incidence angles used for polarimetric data acquisition (i.e., 26° vs. 34°).

5. Conclusions

The properties of polarimetric target decomposition metrics from burned Mediterranean pine forests were investigated for C- and L-band fully polarimetric acquisitions and the influence of incidence angle and

weather conditions on the response were briefly studied. The potential of burn severity estimation using a unified multiple regression model and target decomposition components was also studied and a comparison with backscatter intensities response was carried out.

According to our experiment we found that for C-band data acquired at steep incidence the anisotropy (i.e., Cloude-Pottier decomposition) and double bounce (i.e., van Zyl decomposition) components were better correlated with burn severity levels. For C-band data acquired at shallower angles, the scattering properties from burned areas change and better relationships with burn severity levels were obtained for entropy (i.e., Cloude-Pottier decomposition) and volume scattering (i.e., Yamaguchi and van Zyl decompositions) components. At L-band, volume scattering was better related to burn severity levels despite the steep acquisition geometry with low correlations or non-significant relationships being observed for polarimetric components related to surface scattering mechanisms.

Relatively high determination coefficients and low estimation errors of burn severity were obtained for all datasets with L-band data presenting the highest sensitivity to burn severity levels. A multiple regression model accounting for the interaction of the local topography provided sufficient accuracy for burn severity estimation. For our particular study sites fully polarimetric acquisition improved marginally the estimation accuracy of forest burn severity with respect to dual-pol backscatter intensities (in particular HV-channel). The advantage of using scattering mechanisms could reside in an automatic cartography of burn severity levels without the need of costly field data. By selecting unburned areas as reference one could reliably differentiate burn severity levels using the alpha/entropy space.

Acknowledgments

The study was conducted under an Australian Research Council (ARC) Superscience Fellowship (FS100100040) and was supported by the Cooperative Research Centre for Spatial Information. The Radarsat-2 datasets were provided by the CSA-ESA under the SOAR-EU 6793 project. The ALOS PALSAR dataset was provided by JAXA under the Kyoto and Carbon Initiative.

References

- [1] M. O. Andreae and P. Merlet, "Emission of trace gases and aerosols from biomass burning," *Global Biogeochemical Cycles*, vol. 15, pp. 955-966, 2001.
- [2] J. L. Allen and B. Sorbel, "Assessing the differenced Normalized Burn Ratio's ability to map burn severity in the boreal forest and tundra ecosystems of Alaska's national parks," *International Journal of Wildland Fire*, vol. 17, pp. 463-475, 2008.
- [3] E. S. Kasischke, M. R. Turetsky, R. D. Ottmar, N. H. F. French, E. E. Hoy, and E. S. Kane, "Evaluation of the composite burn index for assessing fire severity in Alaskan black spruce forests," *International Journal of Wildland Fire*, vol. 17, pp. 515-526, 2008.
- [4] A. de Santis and E. Chuvieco, "Burn severity estimation from remotely sensed data: Performance of simulation versus empirical models," *Remote Sensing of Environment*, vol. 108, pp. 422-435, 2007.
- [5] M. A. Tanase, J. de la Riva, M. Santoro, T. Le Toan, and F. Perez-Cabello, "Sensitivity of X-, C- and L-band SAR backscatter to fire severity in mediterranean pine forests," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 48, pp. 3663-3675, 2010.
- [6] C. H. Key and N. C. Benson, "Landscape assessment (LA) Sampling and Analysis Methods," U.S. Department of Agriculture, Forest Service, Rocky Mountain Research Station, Gen. Tech. Rep. RMRS-GTR-164-CD, Fort Collins, CO 2006.
- [7] M. A. Wulder, J. C. White, F. Alvarez, T. Han, J. Rogan, and B. Hawkes, "Characterizing boreal forest wildfire with multi-temporal Landsat and LIDAR data," *Remote Sensing of Environment*, vol. 113, pp. 1540-1555, 2009.
- [8] M. Tanase, J. de la Riva, and F. Pérez-Cabello, "Estimating burn severity at the regional level using optically based indices," *Canadian Journal of Forest Research*, vol. 41, pp. 863-872, 2011.
- [9] D. L. Verbyla, E. S. Kasischke, and E. E. Hoy, "Seasonal and topographic effects on estimating fire severity from Landsat TM/ETM+ data " *International Journal of Wildland Fire*, vol. 17, pp. 527-534, 2008.
- [10] L. L. Bourgeau-Chavez, P. A. Harrell, E. S. Kasischke, and N. H. F. French, "The detection and mapping of Alaskan wildfires using a spaceborne imaging radar system," *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, vol. 18, pp. 355-373, 1997.
- [11] L. L. Bourgeau-Chavez, E. S. Kasischke, S. Brunzell, and J. P. Mudd, "Mapping fire scars in global boreal forests using imaging radar data," *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, vol. 23, pp. 4211-4234, 2002.
- [12] C. H. Menges, R. E. Bartolo, D. Bell, and G. J. E. Hill, "The effect of savanna fires on SAR backscatter in northern Australia," *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, vol. 25, pp. 4857-4871, 2004.

- [13] F. Siegert and G. Ruecker, "Use of multitemporal ERS-2 SAR images for identification of burned scars in south-east Asian tropical rainforest," *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, vol. 21, pp. 831-837, 2000.
- [14] L. L. Bourgeau-Chavez, E. S. Kasischke, N. H. F. French, L. H. Szeto, and C. M. Kherkher, "Using ERS-1 SAR Imagery to Monitor Variations in Burn Severity in an Alaskan Fire-Disturbed Boreal Forest Ecosystem," *Proc. Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium, 1994. IGARSS '94. Proceedings. 1994 IEEE International Pasadena, California, 1994*.
- [15] K. R. Czuchlewski and J. K. Weissel, "Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR)-based mapping of wildfire burn severity and recovery," in *Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium, 2005. IGARSS '05. Proceedings. 2005 IEEE International* vol. 1. Seoul, Korea, 2005.
- [16] F. Siegert and A. A. Hoffmann, "The 1998 Forest Fires in East Kalimantan (Indonesia): A Quantitative Evaluation Using High Resolution, Multitemporal ERS-2 SAR Images and NOAA-AVHRR Hotspot Data," *Remote Sensing of Environment*, vol. 72, pp. 64-77, 2000.
- [17] M. A. Tanase, F. Pérez-Cabello, J. de la Riva, and M. Santoro, "TerraSAR-X data for burn severity evaluation in Mediterranean forests on sloped terrain," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 48, pp. 917-929, 2010.
- [18] M. A. Tanase, M. Santoro, J. de la Riva, and F. Pérez-Cabello, "Backscatter properties of multitemporal TerraSAR-X data and the effects of influencing factors on burn severity evaluation, in a Mediterranean pine forest," *Proc. Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium, 2009. IGARSS '09. 2009 IEEE International Cape Town, South Africa, 2009*.
- [19] M. A. Tanase, M. Santoro, U. Wegmüller, J. de la Riva, and F. Perez-Cabello, "Properties of X-, C- and L-band repeat-pass interferometric SAR coherence in Mediterranean pine forests affected by fires," *Remote Sensing of Environment*, vol. 114, pp. 2182-2194, 2010.
- [20] M. Tanase, M. Santoro, J. de la Riva, E. Kasischke, and M. A. Korets, "L-band SAR backscatter prospects for burn severity estimation in boreal forests," *Proc. ESA Living Planet Symposium*, Bergen, Norway, 2010.
- [21] A. Freeman and S. L. Durden, "A Three-Component Scattering Model for Polarimetric SAR Data," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 36, pp. 963-973, 1998.
- [22] Y. Yamaguchi, T. Moriyama, M. I. Hiroyoshi, and Y. Shinji, "Four-Component Scattering Model for Polarimetric SAR Image Decomposition," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 43, pp. 1699-1706, 2005.
- [23] J. J. van Zyl, M. Arii, and Y. Kim, "Model-Based Decomposition of Polarimetric SAR Covariance Matrices Constrained for Nonnegative Eigenvalues," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 49, pp. 3452-3459, 2011.
- [24] S. R. Cloude, "Uniqueness of Target Decomposition Theorem in Radar Polarimetry," in *Direct and Inverse Methods in Radar Polarimetry*, NATO-ARW, W. M. Boerner, H. Brand, L. A. Cram, D. E. Stein, W. Wiesbeck, W. Keidel, D. Giuli, D. T. Gjessing, and F. A. Molinet, Eds.: Kluwer Academic Publishers, 1992, pp. 267-296.
- [25] S. R. Cloude and E. Pottier, "An Entropy Based Classification Scheme for Land Applications of Polarimetric SAR," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 35, pp. 68-78, 1997.
- [26] S. R. Cloude and E. Pottier, "A Review of Target Decomposition Theorems in radar Polarimetry," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 34, pp. 498-518, 1996.
- [27] U. Wegmüller, C. Werner, T. Strozzi, and A. Wiesmann, "Automated and precise image registration procedures," in *Analysis of multi-temporal remote sensing images*, vol. 2, L. Bruzzone and P. Smits, Eds. Singapore: World Scientific 2002, 2002, pp. 37-49.
- [28] O. Frey, M. Santoro, C. L. Werner, and U. Wegmüller, "DEM-Based SAR Pixel-Area Estimation for Enhanced Geocoding Refinement and Radiometric Normalization," *Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters, IEEE*, vol. 10, pp. 48-52, 2013.
- [29] C. H. Key and N. C. Benson, *Ground Measure of Severity, The Composite Burn Index*. Ogden, UT: U.S. Department of Agriculture, Forest Service, Rocky Mountain Research Station, 2004.
- [30] R. G. Allen, L. S. Pereira, D. Raes, and M. Smith, "Crop Evapotranspiration: Guidelines for Computing Crop Water Requirement," vol. United Nations Food and Agriculture, Organization, Irrigation and Drainage Paper 56, Rome, Italy, 1998, pp. 300.
- [31] J. J. van Zyl, M. Arii, and Y. Kim, "Requirements for model-based polarimetric decompositions," *Proc. Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium, 2008. IGARSS '08. 2008 IEEE International Boston, 2008*.
- [32] J.S. Lee, M. R. Grunes, D. L. Schuler, E. Pottier, and L. Ferro-Famil, "Scattering-Model-Based Speckle Filtering of Polarimetric SAR Data," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 44, pp. 176-187, 2006.

Figure 1 Study area and the forest fire sites (left) and detail around Zaragoza city (center). The background is represented by the MODIS Vegetation continuous fields (VCF) dataset showing forested areas. The burn severity expressed by the dNBR index was overlaid on a false color composite of pre-fire Landsat TM images (insert right).

Figure 2 2-D feature space representations of burn severity levels expressed by the dNBR index (flat or nearly-flat areas). The intensities correspond to backscatter and polarimetric decomposition components. The top and center panels represent C-band polarimetric data acquired at 26° and 43° incidence angle, respectively. The bottom panel represents ALOS PALSAR data acquired at 28° incidence angle. Volume, surface and dihedral scattering correspond to van Zyl model decomposition.

Figure 3 Average H and α with respect to the local incidence angle for unburned, medium burned and highly burned areas. Top panels represent C-band Radarsat-2 data while lower panels represent L-band ALOS PALSAR data. Images acquired under wet conditions are depicted by filled circles. The vertical bars represent the standard deviation of the mean.

Table 1 SAR data characteristics and processing parameters

	Radarsat-2	PALSAR
Band/ wavelength [cm]	C- [5.6]	L- [23.6]
Acquisition mode	Fine Quad	Polarimetric
Incidence angle	28 ⁰ or 43 ⁰	26 ⁰
Azimuth pixel spacing (m)	4.7	3.8
Range/azimuth pixel spacing (m)	4.7 or 5.5	9.4
Multi-look factors (range/azimuth)	3/7 or 5/6	2/8
Pixel spacing (map geometry)		25
Projection/Ellipsoid	UTM Zone30 /International 1924	
Datum	European 1950	

Table 2 SAR acquisition dates and climatic data (Accumulated Precipitations AcPp-[mm], temperature T-[°C]), relative humidity H₀-[%] and reference evapotranspiration ET₀ – [mm/day] recorded at nearby meteorological stations. Data recorded during the 24 hour period before SAR acquisition are presented in parenthesis.

Sensor / acquisition date	AcPp	T	H ₀	ET ₀
Radarsat-2 / 2009.12.26	16.1(11.1)	4.9	96.0	0.7
Radarsat-2 / 2010.01.19	1.6 (0.0)	7.8	95.3	0.5
Radarsat-2 / 2010.03.11	0.0 (0.0)	1.8	56.0	2.1
Radarsat-2 / 2010.04.04	5.8 (4.0)	10.5	41.6	3.5
PALSAR / 2009.04.28	3.5 (2.5)*	6.6	74.8	4.0

*data obtained from the automatic range gauge located at the center of the fire perimeter

Table 3 Correlation coefficients between selected SAR metrics and burn severity. Not significant relationship (p>0.01) marked as *ns*.

Decomposition	Metric	2009.12.26 ¹	2010.01.19 ¹	2010.03.11 ²	2010.04.04 ²	2009.04.28 ³
Pauli	HH-VV	0.33	0.31	<i>ns</i>	<i>ns</i>	<i>ns</i>
	HH+VV	0.44	0.21	-0.67	-0.61	-0.78
	2HV	0.23	<i>ns</i>	-0.70	-0.62	-0.78
Freeman-Durden	Odd	0.49	0.55	0.66	0.71	0.34
	Double	0.58	0.54	-0.34	<i>ns</i>	-0.40
	Volume	0.39	<i>ns</i>	-0.78	-0.75	-0.83
van Zyl	Odd	0.47	0.47	0.29	0.32	0.09
	Double	0.69	0.49	-0.71	-0.65	-0.79
	Volume	0.36	<i>ns</i>	-0.79	-0.76	-0.83
Yamaguchi	Odd	0.47	0.48	0.30	0.33	0.10
	Double	0.70	0.48	-0.73	-0.67	-0.80
	Volume	0.36	<i>ns</i>	-0.79	-0.76	-0.83
Cloude	T11	0.43	0.41	<i>ns</i>	<i>ns</i>	<i>ns</i>
	T22	0.45	0.27	-0.67	-0.53	-0.70
	T33	0.11	-0.24	-0.75	-0.70	-0.76
Cloude-Pottier	H	-0.35	-0.47	-0.81	-0.81	-0.48
	A	0.70	0.68	0.62	0.68	0.74
	α	-0.32	-0.47	-0.82	-0.80	-0.51
Backscatter intensity	HH	0.62	0.55	-0.29	-0.36	-0.23
	HV	0.51	<i>ns</i>	-0.87	-0.84	-0.86
	VV	0.48	0.44	-0.46	-0.48	-0.21

* ¹ Radarsat-2 acquired at 28 degrees incidence angle // ² Radarsat-2 acquired at 43 degrees incidence angle // ³ ALOS PALSAR.

Table 4 Determination coefficient explaining the agreement between burn severity and selected TD and BI metrics together with the root mean squared error (RMSE) and the agreement between observed and predicted burned severity values for each SAR metric analyzed. In bold the best estimates by metric type (TD and respectively BI metrics) and acquisition date.

Image date	Polarimetric target decomposition metrics												Backscatter intensity metrics			
	Pauli			Freeman-Durden			van Zyl			Cloude-Pottier			HH	HV	VV	
	HH-VV	HH+VV	2HV	Odd	Double	Volume	Odd	Double	Volume	H	A	α	HH	HV	VV	
<i>Determination coefficient (model R²) of the multi-linear regression model</i>																
2009.12.26 ¹	0.48	0.47	0.30	0.58	0.36	0.51	0.61	0.55	0.47	0.32	0.56	0.28	0.65	0.31	0.48	
2010.01.19 ¹	0.47	0.26	0.06	0.63	0.32	0.08	0.61	0.40	0.06	0.52	0.46	0.51	0.60	0.06	0.45	
2010.03.11 ²	0.02	0.75	0.78	0.70	0.15	0.84	0.40	0.71	0.84	0.77	0.42	0.78	0.07	0.77	0.23	
2010.04.04 ²	0.05	0.71	0.72	0.69	0.03	0.79	0.32	0.64	0.79	0.73	0.43	0.73	0.20	0.71	0.29	
2009.04.28 ³	0.06	0.80	0.81	0.35	0.21	0.83	0.03	0.79	0.84	0.49	0.58	0.53	0.16	0.78	0.17	
<i>Root mean squared Error (RMSE) of the model</i>																
2009.12.26 ¹	228	217	273	214	247	213	192	196	229	252	229	258	190	255	225	
2010.01.19 ¹	224	299	307	188	259	305	192	254	307	227	225	232	198	307	227	
2010.03.11 ²	306	163	168	187	293	148	260	183	147	158	244	157	289	159	267	
2010.04.04 ²	286	181	168	181	296	147	261	199	147	160	208	164	268	169	239	
2009.04.28 ³	290	131	134	241	256	122	298	139	121	206	193	198	266	151	267	
<i>Determination coefficient (predicted R²) between predicted and observed dNBR values</i>																
2009.12.26 ¹	0.43	0.49	0.20	0.50	0.33	0.50	0.60	0.59	0.43	0.31	0.43	0.28	0.61	0.29	0.44	
2010.01.19 ¹	0.45	0.11	0.01	0.62	0.28	0.01	0.60	0.33	0.01	0.44	0.45	0.41	0.57	0.01	0.44	
2010.03.11 ²	0.07	0.74	0.73	0.65	0.14	0.78	0.32	0.66	0.79	0.75	0.39	0.76	0.18	0.75	0.29	
2010.04.04 ²	0.11	0.65	0.69	0.64	0.03	0.76	0.26	0.57	0.76	0.72	0.52	0.70	0.21	0.69	0.37	
2009.04.28 ³	0.07	0.81	0.80	0.36	0.27	0.84	0.01	0.79	0.84	0.54	0.59	0.57	0.23	0.75	0.22	

¹ Radarsat-2 acquired at 28 degrees incidence angle // ² Radarsat-2 acquired at 43 degrees incidence angle // ³ ALOS PALSAR